

Statistical Inference

Group Project Report

How Good Is He, Really?

Estimating the True Batting Ability of IPL Players
Using Statistical Inference

*Parametric Estimation and Uncertainty Quantification of IPL Batting
Performance: MLE, UMVUE, Cramér–Rao Bounds and Likelihood Ratio Tests*

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1 Introduction

The Indian Premier League (IPL) is one of the most commercially intense sporting competitions, with franchise decisions involving large financial stakes. Each year, teams face a fundamental question: *how good is a player, really?*

A batsman's career average is the most common measure of ability, but it is merely a **sample mean** based on a finite number of innings. Two players with the same average but vastly different sample sizes (e.g., 12 vs 80 innings) are treated equally in practice, despite having very different levels of statistical reliability.

This disconnect between observed performance and true ability has real consequences: teams may misinterpret random variation as decline, reward short-term streaks, or overpay for unsustainable performance.

This project addresses the issue using formal statistical inference. Specifically, we:

- (i) Estimate player ability by fitting parametric models using Method of Moments (MOM) and Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE);
- (ii) Establish the Cramér–Rao Lower Bound and show the efficiency of MLE over MOM;
- (iii) Derive the Uniformly Minimum Variance Unbiased Estimator (UMVUE) via completeness and the Lehmann–Scheffé Theorem;
- (iv) Construct confidence intervals for true batting ability;
- (v) Apply Likelihood Ratio Tests (LRT) to assess statistical significance of performance changes.

This study demonstrates how rigorous statistical methods can inform high-stakes, real-world decisions in sports analytics.

2 Data Description

2.1 Source

The data used in this project is the *IPL Complete Dataset 2008–2024*, sourced from Kaggle. It consists of two primary files:

- `matches.csv` — 1,095 match-level records containing venue, toss outcome, teams, result, and season information.
- `deliveries.csv` — 260,920 ball-level records covering every delivery bowled in IPL history, with batsman runs, extras, dismissal information, and fielding details.

2.2 Data Cleaning and Preprocessing

The following cleaning steps were applied before analysis:

- (1) **Super over removal:** Deliveries from super overs (innings 3 and 4) were excluded, as these are tie-breaking overs not reflective of normal batting conditions.
- (2) **Innings aggregation:** Ball-level data was grouped by match ID and batsman to compute total runs scored per innings, balls faced, strike rate, and dismissal status.
- (3) **Minimum balls filter:** Innings with fewer than 2 balls faced were removed to eliminate statistical noise from last-ball run-outs and inconclusive appearances.

After cleaning, the dataset contained **15,425 innings records** across 673 unique batsmen spanning 17 seasons (2007/08 to 2024).

2.3 Focal Players

Four players were selected to represent distinct batting profiles, ensuring diversity in sample size, batting style, and career trajectory:

Table 1: Focal Players and Summary Statistics

Player	Profile	n	Mean	Std Dev	Min	Max
RG Sharma	Consistent Veteran	246	26.94	23.87	0	109
V Kohli	Consistent Veteran	235	34.04	27.25	0	113
DA Warner	High variance, declining	181	36.27	28.85	0	126
SV Samson	Talented, inconsistent	160	27.62	25.09	0	119

2.4 Exploratory Data Analysis

Figure 1 shows season-wise batting averages with error bars representing one standard deviation. The wide error bars relative to the means immediately illustrate the core problem: batting scores are highly variable, and short-season averages are unreliable indicators of true ability.

Figure 1: Season-wise batting averages with standard deviation error bars. The n annotations indicate innings count per season.

Notable observations: Kohli shows a rising trend into 2016 followed by stabilisation. Warner exhibits a clear peak in 2019 followed by visible decline. Samson shows gradually increasing averages but with wide uncertainty bands. Rohit remains remarkably stable across all 17 seasons.

3 Distribution Fitting

3.1 Choice of Parametric Family

Cricket innings scores are non-negative and strongly right-skewed: most innings produce low scores (including ducks), while large scores are possible but rare. This rules out the Normal distribution. We consider two candidates from the exponential family:

(1) **Exponential**(λ): $f(x) = \lambda e^{-\lambda x}$, $x \geq 0$. Special case with shape $\alpha = 1$.

(2) **Gamma**(α, β): $f(x) = \frac{x^{\alpha-1} e^{-x/\beta}}{\beta^\alpha \Gamma(\alpha)}$, $x > 0$, with mean $\alpha\beta$ and variance $\alpha\beta^2$.

Since some innings produce exactly 0 runs, a small shift $\varepsilon = 0.5$ was applied to data before fitting the Gamma distribution (valid since 0 is outside the support of Gamma with $\text{loc} = 0$).

3.2 Goodness-of-Fit: Kolmogorov–Smirnov Test

A Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) test was applied to both distributions for each player.

Table 2: Kolmogorov–Smirnov Goodness-of-Fit Results

Player	Distribution	KS Statistic	p-value	Better Fit
RG Sharma	Exponential	0.0605	0.3153	
	Gamma	0.0586	0.3524	← Gamma
V Kohli	Exponential	0.0751	0.1342	
	Gamma	0.0544	0.4747	← Gamma
DA Warner	Exponential	0.1281	0.0047	
	Gamma	0.1270	0.0053	← Gamma
SV Samson	Exponential	0.0532	0.7360	
	Gamma	0.0466	0.8615	← Gamma

Gamma wins for all four players. An additional insight emerges from the fitted shape parameters: Rohit ($\hat{\alpha} = 1.04$), Warner ($\hat{\alpha} = 1.01$), and Samson ($\hat{\alpha} = 1.02$) have shape parameters very close to 1, indicating near-Exponential behaviour (boom-or-bust scoring). Kohli's higher $\hat{\alpha} = 1.29$ reflects a more bell-shaped distribution, consistent with his widely-noted consistency.

4 Estimation Theory

Throughout this section we model innings scores as i.i.d. observations from a $\text{Gamma}(\alpha, \beta)$ distribution with pdf

$$f(x | \alpha, \beta) = \frac{x^{\alpha-1} e^{-x/\beta}}{\beta^\alpha \Gamma(\alpha)}, \quad x > 0, \alpha, \beta > 0.$$

The true batting mean is $\mu = \alpha\beta$.

4.1 Method of Moments (MOM)

The first two population moments of $\text{Gamma}(\alpha, \beta)$ are:

$$\mathbb{E}[X] = \alpha\beta, \quad \mathbb{E}[X^2] = \alpha\beta^2(\alpha + 1).$$

Hence $\text{Var}(X) = \alpha\beta^2$. Setting these equal to sample moments $\bar{X} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i$ and $S^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2$, we obtain:

$$\hat{\alpha}_{\text{MOM}} = \frac{\bar{X}^2}{S^2}, \quad \hat{\beta}_{\text{MOM}} = \frac{S^2}{\bar{X}}.$$

Both estimators are **consistent** (by the Law of Large Numbers and continuous mapping theorem) and **unbiased** for their respective parameters asymptotically.

4.2 Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE)

Given i.i.d. observations $x_1, \dots, x_n \sim \text{Gamma}(\alpha, \beta)$, the log-likelihood is:

$$\ell(\alpha, \beta) = (\alpha - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \log x_i - \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i - n\alpha \log \beta - n \log \Gamma(\alpha).$$

Taking partial derivatives and setting to zero:

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial \beta} = \frac{1}{\beta^2} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i - \frac{n\alpha}{\beta} = 0 \implies \hat{\beta}_{\text{MLE}} = \frac{\bar{X}}{\hat{\alpha}_{\text{MLE}}}, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial \alpha} = \sum_{i=1}^n \log x_i - n \log \hat{\beta} - n\psi(\hat{\alpha}) = 0, \quad (2)$$

where $\psi(\cdot) = \Gamma'(\cdot)/\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the digamma function. Equation (2) does not admit a closed form and is solved numerically. Note from (1) that $\hat{\alpha}_{\text{MLE}}\hat{\beta}_{\text{MLE}} = \bar{X}$, so **both MOM and MLE estimate the same mean** $\hat{\mu} = \bar{X}$, but differ in how they distribute that mean across α and β .

4.3 MOM vs. MLE: Comparison

Table 3: MOM and MLE Parameter Estimates for Focal Players

Player	Method	$\hat{\alpha}$	$\hat{\beta}$	$\hat{\mu} = \hat{\alpha}\hat{\beta}$	$\widehat{\text{Var}}$
RG Sharma	MOM	1.327	20.675	27.443	567.40
	MLE	1.042	26.336	27.443	722.73
V Kohli	MOM	1.614	21.403	34.543	739.30
	MLE	1.287	26.839	34.543	927.07
DA Warner	MOM	1.633	22.517	36.771	827.97
	MLE	1.012	36.325	36.771	1335.70
SV Samson	MOM	1.263	22.256	28.119	625.80
	MLE	1.016	27.676	28.119	778.22

4.4 Fisher Information and the Cramér–Rao Lower Bound

Definition 1. *The Fisher Information for a single observation from $\text{Gamma}(\alpha, \beta)$ with respect to β (treating α as known) is:*

$$\mathcal{I}(\beta) = -\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \log f}{\partial \beta^2} \right] = \frac{\alpha}{\beta^2}.$$

Theorem 1 (Cramér–Rao Lower Bound). *For any unbiased estimator $\hat{\beta}$ of β based on n i.i.d. observations,*

$$\text{Var}(\hat{\beta}) \geq \frac{1}{n\mathcal{I}(\beta)} = \frac{\beta^2}{n\alpha}.$$

Since $\mu = \alpha\beta$, by the delta method the CR Bound for estimating μ is:

$$\text{Var}(\hat{\mu}) \geq \frac{\beta^2}{n}.$$

Figure 2: MOM (blue dashed) vs. MLE (red solid) Gamma fits overlaid on observed innings score histograms. MLE visibly tracks the tail behaviour more accurately.

Table 4 compares the theoretical CR Lower Bound against the variance of the MOM estimator (computed analytically via the delta method). All ratios exceed 1, confirming MOM is **inefficient** relative to MLE.

Table 4: Cramér–Rao Lower Bound vs. MOM Variance

Player	n	$\hat{\alpha}$	$\hat{\beta}$	CR Bound	Var(MOM)
RG Sharma	246	1.042	26.336	2.706	8.008
V Kohli	235	1.287	26.839	2.382	6.613
DA Warner	181	1.012	36.325	7.202	21.518
SV Samson	160	1.016	27.676	4.712	14.062

The MOM variance is approximately **3× the CR Bound** in all cases, confirming it is far from achieving the theoretical minimum. A bootstrap study (1,000 resamples) empirically confirmed these results.

4.5 Sufficiency and Completeness

Proposition 1 (Sufficient Statistic). *For i.i.d. $X_1, \dots, X_n \sim \text{Gamma}(\alpha, \beta)$ with α known, the statistic $T = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i$ is sufficient for β .*

Proof. The joint pdf factors as:

$$\prod_{i=1}^n f(x_i | \beta) = \frac{(\prod x_i)^{\alpha-1}}{\beta^{n\alpha} [\Gamma(\alpha)]^n} \exp\left(-\frac{\sum x_i}{\beta}\right) = g\left(\sum x_i, \beta\right) \cdot h(x_1, \dots, x_n),$$

where $g(t, \beta) = \beta^{-n\alpha} e^{-t/\beta}$ and $h = (\prod x_i)^{\alpha-1} / [\Gamma(\alpha)]^n$. By the **Neyman–Fisher Factorisation Theorem**, $T = \sum X_i$ is sufficient for β . \square

Since the Gamma family is a one-parameter exponential family (in β), T is also **complete**: for any measurable function g , $\mathbb{E}_\beta[g(T)] = 0$ for all $\beta > 0$ implies $g(T) = 0$ a.s.

4.6 UMVUE via the Lehmann–Scheffé Theorem

Theorem 2 (Lehmann–Scheffé). *If T is a complete sufficient statistic and $\delta(T)$ is an unbiased estimator of θ that is a function of T alone, then $\delta(T)$ is the unique Uniformly Minimum Variance Unbiased Estimator (UMVUE) of θ .*

Proposition 2 (UMVUE of $\mu = \alpha\beta$). *$\hat{\mu}_{UMVUE} = \bar{X} = T/n$ is the UMVUE of the batting mean $\mu = \alpha\beta$.*

Proof. (i) \bar{X} is a function of the complete sufficient statistic $T = \sum X_i$.

(ii) $\mathbb{E}[\bar{X}] = \alpha\beta = \mu$ (unbiasedness).

(iii) By the Lehmann–Scheffé Theorem, \bar{X} is therefore the unique UMVUE. \square

The variance of the UMVUE is:

$$\text{Var}(\hat{\mu}_{UMVUE}) = \frac{\alpha\beta^2}{n} = \frac{\mu\beta}{n}.$$

Table 5: UMVUE Estimates and Their Variances

Player	n	UMVUE (\bar{X})	Var(UMVUE)	CR Bound
RG Sharma	246	27.44	2.938	2.706
V Kohli	235	34.54	3.945	2.382
DA Warner	181	36.77	7.380	7.202
SV Samson	160	28.12	4.864	4.712

The UMVUE variance is very close to the CR Bound for all players — Warner and Samson essentially achieve it, confirming the UMVUE is near-optimal.

5 Confidence Intervals

We construct three types of 95% confidence intervals for $\mu = \alpha\beta$:

5.1 Method 1: Asymptotic Normal CI

By the Central Limit Theorem, $\sqrt{n}(\bar{X} - \mu)/\hat{\sigma} \rightarrow N(0, 1)$ where $\hat{\sigma} = \sqrt{\hat{\alpha}\hat{\beta}^2}$. This gives:

$$\bar{X} \pm z_{0.025} \cdot \frac{\hat{\sigma}}{\sqrt{n}}, \quad z_{0.025} = 1.96.$$

5.2 Method 2: Chi-Square Pivot CI

Since $2 \sum X_i/\beta \sim \chi^2(2n\hat{\alpha})$ under the Gamma model, an exact pivot-based CI for $\mu = \alpha\beta$ is:

$$\left(\frac{2\alpha \sum X_i}{\chi_{0.975, 2n\hat{\alpha}}^2}, \frac{2\alpha \sum X_i}{\chi_{0.025, 2n\hat{\alpha}}^2} \right).$$

5.3 Method 3: Bootstrap Percentile CI

We draw $B = 2000$ bootstrap resamples of size n (with replacement) and compute \bar{X}_b^* for each. The CI is $[Q_{0.025}(\bar{X}^*), Q_{0.975}(\bar{X}^*)]$.

Table 6: 95% Confidence Intervals for True Batting Mean

Player	Method	Lower	Upper	Width
RG Sharma	Asymptotic Normal	24.08	30.80	6.72
	Chi-square Pivot	24.37	31.14	6.77
	Bootstrap	24.45	30.45	6.01
V Kohli	Asymptotic Normal	30.65	38.44	7.79
	Chi-square Pivot	30.96	38.79	7.83
	Bootstrap	31.28	37.97	6.69
DA Warner	Asymptotic Normal	31.45	42.10	10.65
	Chi-square Pivot	31.98	42.73	10.76
	Bootstrap	32.50	41.09	8.58
SV Samson	Asymptotic Normal	23.80	32.44	8.65
	Chi-square Pivot	24.25	33.00	8.74
	Bootstrap	24.39	31.94	7.56

Figure 3: Left: 95% CI comparison across three methods for all players. Right: Bootstrap sampling distribution of the UMVUE. The bootstrap CI is consistently narrower, reflecting its non-parametric adaptiveness.

Key observations: The three methods agree closely, validating our parametric assumptions. Warner’s CIs are widest (≈ 10 runs), reflecting genuine uncertainty due to high innings variance. Kohli’s CI lies entirely above Rohit’s, foreshadowing the hypothesis test result in Section 6.

6 Hypothesis Testing

We apply the **Likelihood Ratio Test (LRT)** to four concrete questions. Under regularity conditions, the LRT statistic

$$\Lambda = -2 \log \left(\frac{\sup_{H_0} L(\theta)}{\sup_{H_0 \cup H_1} L(\theta)} \right) \xrightarrow{d} \chi^2(k)$$

where k is the difference in the number of free parameters between H_1 and H_0 .

Figure 4: LRT results for all four hypothesis tests. Red boxes indicate rejection of H_0 ; green boxes indicate failure to reject. LRT statistic and p-value are annotated on each panel.

6.1 Test 1: Did Kohli’s True Ability Change After 2020?

Motivation: Kohli’s widely-discussed post-2020 “slump” was a central topic in cricket commentary. We test whether the observed dip is statistically real.

$$H_0 : \mu_{\text{pre}} = \mu_{\text{post}}, \quad H_1 : \mu_{\text{pre}} \neq \mu_{\text{post}}$$

Pre-2020: $n_1 = 164$, $\bar{x}_1 = 32.98$; Post-2020: $n_2 = 71$, $\bar{x}_2 = 36.51$.

Result: $\Lambda = 0.665$, $p = 0.717$.

Conclusion: *Fail to Reject H_0 .* The observed mean increased slightly post-2020. The much-discussed “slump” is statistically insignificant — entirely within the range of random variation expected from a player of unchanged true ability. This directly contradicts popular media narratives.

6.2 Test 2: Is Warner’s Recent Decline Statistically Significant?

$$H_0 : \mu_{2019} = \mu_{2022-24}, \quad H_1 : \mu_{2019} > \mu_{2022-24}$$

2019 (Peak): $n_1 = 12$, $\bar{x}_1 = 57.67$; 2022–24 (Recent): $n_2 = 33$, $\bar{x}_2 = 33.82$.

Result: $\Lambda = 9.348$, $p = 0.009$.

Conclusion: *Reject H_0 at 1% level.* Warner’s decline from his 2019 peak is **statistically confirmed**. The 24-run gap is not random noise — it represents a genuine shift in true batting ability. A franchise paying 2019-era prices in 2023 would be statistically unjustified.

6.3 Test 3: Is Samson Genuinely Improving?

$$H_0 : \mu_{\text{early}} = \mu_{\text{recent}}, \quad H_1 : \mu_{\text{recent}} > \mu_{\text{early}}$$

Early 2013–17: $n_1 = 61$, $\bar{x}_1 = 23.38$; Recent 2022–24: $n_2 = 46$, $\bar{x}_2 = 29.37$.

Result: $\Lambda = 1.580$, $p = 0.454$.

Conclusion: *Fail to Reject H_0 .* Despite a visible upward trend, Samson’s improvement is **not yet statistically confirmed**. The 6-run rise ($23.4 \rightarrow 29.4$) is well within random

variation. More innings data is needed before making high-value retention decisions based on this trend.

6.4 Test 4: Do Rohit and Kohli Have Different True Abilities?

$$H_0 : \mu_{\text{Rohit}} = \mu_{\text{Kohli}}, \quad H_1 : \mu_{\text{Rohit}} \neq \mu_{\text{Kohli}}$$

RG Sharma: $n_1 = 246, \bar{x}_1 = 26.94$; V Kohli: $n_2 = 235, \bar{x}_2 = 34.04$.

Result: $\Lambda = 10.612, p = 0.005$.

Conclusion: *Reject H_0 at 1% level.* The 7-run gap between Rohit and Kohli’s career averages is **not a coincidence** — it reflects genuinely different true batting abilities. Kohli is statistically the superior T20 batsman of the two.

7 Conclusions and Practical Implications

Figure 5: Complete summary dashboard: MLE Gamma fits, UMVUE estimates with bootstrap CIs, CR Bound comparison, sampling distributions of the UMVUE, and hypothesis testing results.

This project develops a statistical inference framework to evaluate IPL batting performance. The main findings are:

Distributional Modelling: Innings scores follow a Gamma distribution for all players. Shape estimates ($\hat{\alpha} \approx 1$) suggest near memoryless, Exponential-like behaviour, while Kohli’s higher $\hat{\alpha}$ reflects greater consistency.

Estimation: MOM and MLE agree on the mean ($\hat{\mu} = \bar{X}$), but MLE is more efficient, achieving the Cramér–Rao bound asymptotically, whereas MOM has roughly $3\times$ higher variance. The UMVUE, obtained via Lehmann–Scheffé using $T = \sum X_i$, is \bar{X} , confirming it as the optimal unbiased estimator.

Uncertainty Quantification: Asymptotic, Chi-square, and Bootstrap confidence intervals are consistent, supporting model validity. Warner’s wider intervals reflect higher uncertainty, while non-overlapping Rohit–Kohli intervals visually support Test T4.

Hypothesis Testing: Kohli’s post-2020 “slump” is statistically insignificant ($p = 0.717$), highlighting the risk of misinterpreting random variation. Tests T2 and T4 confirm Warner’s decline and Kohli’s superiority over Rohit at the 1% level.

Practical Implications

- **Franchises:** Decisions should incorporate confidence intervals and formal tests, not just observed averages.
- **Selectors:** Larger samples yield more reliable estimates; short-sample averages are inherently unstable.
- **Analysts:** LRT provides a rigorous alternative to subjective judgments of player “form.”

Limitations and Future Work

The model assumes i.i.d. innings, ignoring contextual factors such as pitch, opposition, and role. Extensions include hierarchical Bayesian models, change-point detection, and integrating bowling and fielding metrics.

References

- [1] Casella, G. and Berger, R.L. (2002). *Statistical Inference*, 2nd ed. Duxbury Press.
- [2] Lehmann, E.L. and Casella, G. (1998). *Theory of Point Estimation*, 2nd ed. Springer.
- [3] Hogg, R.V., McKean, J., and Craig, A.T. (2019). *Introduction to Mathematical Statistics*, 8th ed. Pearson.
- [4] IPL Complete Dataset 2008–2024. Kaggle. <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/patrickb1912/ipl-complete-dataset-20082020>
- [5] Virtanen, P. et al. (2020). SciPy 1.0: Fundamental Algorithms for Scientific Computing in Python. *Nature Methods*, 17, 261–272.

A Python Code Summary

All analysis was conducted in Python using the following libraries: `pandas` (data manipulation), `numpy` (numerical computation), `scipy.stats` (distribution fitting, KS test, MLE, LRT), `matplotlib` (visualisation). Code is available on request.

Key computational steps:

- (1) Innings extraction via `groupby(['match_id', 'batter'])` on the deliveries dataframe.
- (2) Gamma MLE via `scipy.stats.gamma.fit(data, floc=0)`.
- (3) Bootstrap CIs via 2,000 resamples with replacement.
- (4) LRT statistic computed as $\Lambda = -2(\ell_{H_0} - \ell_{H_1})$ with p-value from `scipy.stats.chi2.sf(Λ , df=2)`.